

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LABOR MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN AND THE ROLE OF EMPLOYMENT IN OUR ECONOMY

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Annotation: the article examines the statistical analysis of the labor market, the issues of employment in the economy, the formation of relevant conclusions and recommendations of the prevention of unemployment.

Key words: employment, unemployment, John Maynard Keynes, The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money, able-bodied, socio-economic system, labor market.

Introduction. One of the effective mechanisms to ensure rational employment and reduce unemployment is the targeted formation and development of the labor market and its regulation. It is necessary to identify the integral links and contradictions between labor supply and demand, the criteria for the effectiveness of their cooperation, to determine the main directions of professional development of rural workers and macroeconomic regulation and ultimately the effective development of socio-economic and organizational measures in accordance with the purpose.

John Maynard Keynes, founder of the Keynesian school, described his concept in his book, “The General Theory of Employment, Interest, and Money”. He sees the labor market as a sluggish, statistical system, noting that labor costs are stable enough. The existence of forced unemployment is based on a lack of comprehensive effective demand, which can be eliminated by effective measures of budget and credit-monetary regulation.

The lack of demand is due to the inelasticity of wages to its declining side, as a result of which the volume of production and employment are reduced when demand falls, and nominal wage rates remain unchanged. The state acts as a market regulator, which can eliminate this inequality by increasing or decreasing aggregate demand. Total demand for labor is regulated by investment and production volumes. That is, the labor market is the supply and demand of the able-bodied population that buys and sells the “able-bodied” between the employed and non-employed sections of the working population and contracts that take into account the relationship between employers and their personal interests, is a complex, multifaceted, growing and open socio-economic system of market economy that directly regulates the relationship between.

The results of analysis and discussion. The formation of rational employment of the able-bodied population can be achieved only on the basis of effective development of the labor market and structural reforms in all sectors of the economy. These determine the process of mass release of surplus labor and their inflow into industrial and service sectors and areas of private labor activity, as well as the urban economy, the formation of labor reserves and their mobilization and redistribution on the basis of market mechanisms.

All demographic, social, economic and other aspects of the formation of rational employment are reflected in the following main criteria:

- Achieving a market balance between supply and demand for labor;
- Increase jobs;
- Increase the participation of the economically active population in labor;
- Ensuring labor productivity growth;
- Increase of labor income of the population;
- Reducing unemployment.

These criteria are determined using the following indicators:

- The number of existing and newly created sites;
- The amount of work performed;
- Volume of GDP per capita;
- The number of local and involved labor resources;
- Migration flows of the population;
- Armament of labor with and energy;
- The amount of social infrastructure services;
- Land loading of each agricultural worker;
- Average annual salary;
- Housing;
- Level of qualification and education of labor resources;
- Shift coefficient of use of fixed assets;
- The number of people not employed in social production and the unemployed and the amount of their benefits;
- Satisfaction with the general results of labor and social infrastructure services;
- Different forms of ownership and efficiency of labor organization.

Table 1

The ratio of the number of employed population to the working age population. Employment rate (in %) ²⁰

Regions	2019	2020	2021
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²⁰ State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Republic of Uzbekistan	68.1	66.0	66.9
Republic of Karakalpakstan	62.9	62.0	60.9
Andijan	70.1	66.5	68.2
Bukhara	69.3	68.3	67.3
Jizzakh	67.1	66.2	67.5
Kashkadarya	63.9	60.9	62.2
Navoi	69.5	66.8	68.3
Namangan	66.4	65.0	65.5
Samarkand	65.3	63.2	63.7
Surkhandarya	67.0	63.9	64.5
Syrdarya	68.9	64.8	64.6
Tashkent	71.4	68.2	70.3
Fergana	67.5	65.1	66.2
Khorezm	66.1	63.7	64.0
Tashkent city	80.1	81.7	83.3

Table 2
According to the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. Labor market (thousand people)²¹

Descriptor	2019	2020	2021
Economically active population	14876.4	14797.4	14980.7
Number of Employed population	13541.1	13236.4	13538.9
Employment by economic activity			
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	3544.6	3499.2	3502.1
Industry	1821.5	1809.5	1883.3
Construction	1324.6	1305.6	1286.8
Trade	1436.4	1405.4	1537.2
Transportation and Storage	646.1	610.5	648.5

²¹State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Education	1134.4	1158.2	1178.3
Health and social services	616.7	669.5	659.0
Other activities	3016.8	2778.5	2843.6

The main goal of the concept of development of the labor market of the republic, which is rich in labor resources, is to reduce employment, increase unemployment, create new jobs, reduce labor productivity, inflation, slow development of various forms of ownership, in the context of the slowness of structural changes in the economy, the decline in real labor incomes, the development of comprehensive measures to increase the demand for labor and reduce its supply. They will be developed based on the strategic goals of deep structural reform and liberalization of the national economy of Uzbekistan in the transition period.

The strategic goals of the concept are as follows:

- Gradual formation of a socially oriented, orderly labor market;
- Development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which will increase the demand for labor and reduce unemployment;
- Strengthening the competitiveness, mobilization and export capacity of local staff, the formation of a class of highly qualified specialists and new economic thinking in the population, the creation of opportunities for free and independent choice of jobs;
- Improvement of organizational, economic and legal mechanisms for regulating the labor market and employment.

Conclusions and suggestions. In the “Development Strategy” adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 28, 2022, developed for 2022-2026, special attention was paid to the development of the labor market and employment. Including significant reforms such as vocational training of graduates and increase in technical colleges, professional development of people. Therefore, it is important to increase employment, reduce unemployment and pursue an active social policy in Uzbekistan and its regions.

Economic growth alone doesn't necessarily translate into more and better jobs, especially for the poor, vulnerable and those at risk of being left behind. Economic growth is a prerequisite for increasing productive employment; it is combined result of increases in labour productivity. Hence, the rate of economic growth sets the absolute ceiling within which growth in employment and growth in labour productivity can take place.

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